

Basic principles of sonication method for detaching viable microorganisms embedded in implant biofilm

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Summary

Ultrasound performance has been used over the last decade for diagnosis of implants related infections, a serious complication of device surgery. It's a relatively novel method, fast developing and much promising on solving diagnostic and therapeutic problems of Clinical Microbiology, and is well known as sonication or ultrasonication. The basic idea of this method is the detachment of alive bacteria from their covering implant biofilm. Formation of biofilm creates serious difficulties in the detection of the causative bacteria of implant related infections by the conventional methods of microbiology and in consequent antimicrobial chemotherapy as well. Detachment is achieved by the use of low frequency ultrasound waves that causes asymmetric cavitation to sonication fluid's microbubbles on the surface of the examined implant. Sonication fluid is then cultured quantitatively or examined by molecular techniques. Description and analysis of the basic principles of the ultrasound method will increase our knowledge about it and help a lot to its improvement and evolution. In this study we revise the basic biological, physics

and technical principles of the assay, as well as its research aspects, and we extract conclusions about its value and perspectives, focusing on diagnosis of implant associated infections.

Key words

implant associated infections, biofilm, sonication, microbubbles, asymmetric cavitation.

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Introduction

Implants replacements initially began to be performed by Sir John Charnley in 1960. Since then infection of artificial devices strongly tend to increase as a result of the continuously elevating number of this kind of operations.¹⁻⁴ Specifically, for knee and hip joint replacements, which are among the most usual ones, the risk of implant related infections is about 1% and for emergency hemiarthroplasties the risk is about 4%.⁵ The risk factors for implants infections are infection of surgical site irrelative to the implant, malignancies, previous arthroplasty operations, cardiopulmonary diseases, and immunosuppression.^{3,6,7} Although infection of used implants is not the more common complication of these operations, it becomes a serious health, social and economic problem.⁸⁻¹⁰

Biofilm are communities of bacteria forming in any case that an aquatic mean, where free-floating individual microorganisms lie, gets in contact to a biotic or abiotic surface.¹¹ It covers underlying bacteria and causes serious difficulties in diagnosis and administration of implant associated infections.^{12,13} Biofilm formation is one of the mechanisms that help bacteria achieve their survival and development in a large variety of conditions.¹¹ Biofilm also plays an important role in the pathophysiology of chronic infectious diseases like cystic fibrosis.¹⁴ Antimicrobial chemotherapy may fail because causative bacteria are protected into biofilm and they develop increased resistance to antimicrobial agents.¹⁵ The biofilm is formed by extra-

cellular exopolysaccharide which is extracted by bacteria cells and adhere on them.^{1,16}

The implementation of low frequency ultrasound waves with an approximately 40 kHz frequency to an implant covered by a solution, can destroy biofilm, as a result of asymmetric cavitation, making possible the detachment of viable bacteria responsible for implant related infections. This method is called sonication.^{17,18} After the performance of the low frequency and intensity ultrasound waves to the implant, which is covered by normal saline or a buffered solution (Ringer's solution), an enriched with biofilm originated viable bacteria fluid is produced, called as "sonication fluid". The sonication fluid is cultured by conventional, quantitative culture methods and/or it proceeds with molecular and/or other non-culture-based methods, in order to detect the pathogens and their antimicrobial resistance.²³ This method is a simple and not expensive one. It seems to be more sensitive and accurate for the diagnosis of prosthetic joint infections compared to conventional cultures of periprosthetic tissue.^{21,22} However, there are 10-20% false negative results when using methods based to the phenotype.²⁴

2. Basic principles of sonication method

The basic biological, physis, and technical principles of the sonication method for the diagnosis of implant associated infections, as well as its clinical and technical research aspects, are described below:

2.1 Biological principles

Biofilm structure is a central concept in biological principles of the sonication method as its destruction and consequent release of alive bacteria is the aim of this method.^{17,18} Its formation is a very important defense mechanism for bacteria and, at the same time, the main cause of diagnostic and therapeutic failures in implant associated infections.²⁵

Biofilm is a microbial community that has served bacterial growth for more than three billion years.²⁶ It can be found in nature like biofilm of rocks in rivers, in human technical structures, like household pipes, and practically everywhere a surface meets aqueous medium containing microorganisms.^{26,27} It also plays an important role in the pathogenesis of diseases like cystic fibrosis, which is of genetic cause and is characterized by the development of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* biofilm in respiratory tracts increasing the infection risk for the patient.²⁸

Its formation procedure is almost the same for bacteria of any species. Free living planktonic bacteria are attached on a surface flowing in an aquatic medium, and they form microcolonies and later a mature community covered by biofilm. Bacteria adhere on surface activated by extracted chemical substances which enforce the attachment and they also act as chemo attractants for other bacterial cells.^{11,29} Adherence proceeds in two steps: cell attachment to the surface and contact between attached cells. At this phase bacteria are called "sessile" cells.³⁰ Under these conditions, bacteria are accumulated, form colonies and are differentiated. Their adherence is achieved mainly by the extraction of exopolysaccharide, a kind of extracellular matrix of slimy construction that consists the 75-90% of biofilms height, and the 50-80% of biofilms organic carbon.^{1,16,31}

As biofilm is growing up changes on bacterial genes expression are observed resulting in colony members communication and regulation of their feeding and growth functions.³²⁻³⁴ Biofilm bacteria perform increased resistance to antibiotics for two main reasons.¹⁵ Firstly because of the usual problem of resistance to antibiotics that's acquired through evolution. This property of bacteria is achieved by mutations that happen when they grow up and divided. When a strain acquires a genetic characteristic that regulates an advantaged metabolism stage which helps it survive in a threat of environment, it has more possibilities to transfer the responsible genes to its progeny and so the species evolve. The newer populations have different genes that make their survival easier relatively to their progenitors.¹ Moreover, biofilm enforces the spread of antibiotic resistance genes because of the dense population of

bacteria.^{30,35,36} The second reason that antimicrobial chemotherapy fails is that even if antibiotics have an action to the outside members of the complex colony of the biofilm, the nucleus of the biofilm remains safe and in this way the effectiveness of antibiotics is severely reduced.^{1,8}

The problem of biofilm-originated bacteria detachment by ultrasound cavitation was addressed almost twenty years ago by Dr Ammy C. Vollmer and Dr E. Carr Everbach. Since then several scientists and engineers have worked on this area. Ultrasound cavitation destructs biofilm through microbubbles directed by ultrasounds.¹⁸ Sonication is a widely used method of lysing bacterial cells. This method exerts its action through bubble activity, heating and shear forces.³⁷ Erythrocytes, platelets, and ovary cells can be damaged by ultrasounds due to membrane rupture and genotoxicity.³⁸⁻⁴⁰ Moreover yeasts, luminous bacteria and dinoflagellates were used experimentally as indicators of damage.⁴¹⁻⁴³ In such an experiment high frequency ultrasound was applied to *Escherichia coli* cultures and the caused damage was evaluated. Destructed bacteria contained stress-relative promoters to their genome activating lux genes producing light after excitement of stress-linked intracellular pathways. The study of this experiment's results has shown that bacterial damage was achieved mainly by two ways: cavitation and high temperature.³⁷ The microjets of liquid, which are produced by the asymmetric kind of cavitation, have the ability to puncture or shear cell walls.^{40,44} In another relative experiment yeast cells were exposed to ultrasound and survival curves have been determined at two different frequencies of irradiation (20 kHz and 1 MHz). The curves were often multi-phasic, with a pronounced 'tail' evident after 1 MHz irradiation. Data from cell size measurements after irradiation and treatment of semi synchronous populations have shown that dividing cells and the largest cells in the population were more sensitive to ultrasound. These relationships can be explained by the tensile stresses that cells undergo in velocity gradients produced by ultrasonically cavitation in the liquido. A quantitative support for this theory is difficult to be performed because estimation of the magnitude of these gradients and comparison to values obtained in pure shear devices are not reliable, due to the non-uniform nature of cavitation ultrasonic fields.⁴ Low-frequency ultrasound waves were also very effective in increasing growth rates of bacterial cultures in vitro,⁴⁶ and action of antibiotics combined to ultrasound as stress inducers to biofilm was proved to be more effective than antibiotics action alone.¹⁵ Actually, it seems that low frequency ultrasound has a double inhibiting and promoting effect in biofilm

viability. The final result depends on ultrasound frequency and intensity, the kind of causative bacteria and other factors.⁴⁷ Although there is data about ultrasound actions to bacterial cultures that show not remarkable effects as antibiotics, other recent experiments on the same subject applied to biofilm *in vitro* have performed important anti-biofilm action by ultrasound.⁴⁸

2.2 Physics principles

The physics principles of the sonication method for breaking biofilm and detaching alive bacteria are based on some classical laws of physics about the properties of gas bubbles in a fluid and especially about the regulation of gas pressure in them.⁴⁹ Specifically, Henry's law supports that the tension of a gas to be dissolved in a liquid is proportional to its partial pressure above liquid at a given temperature. This means that at a stable atmosphere pressure a specific amount of air tends to be diluted in liquid and this phenomenon combined to ultrasound influence, which causes traction and pressure gradients, creates microbubbles. Collapse of microbubbles is accompanied by white noise, luminance and radical formation.⁵⁰ At the case of one microbubble, according to Henry's law if microbubble's pressure is elevated, gas flows out of it and is dissolved into liquid, and on the contrary low pressure inside the microbubble will cause dilution of gas into it because of gases concentration gradient or of vapors of the liquid itself.⁵¹ Gas pressure into bubble is calculated by relative physics laws which support that it is inversely analogous to bubble's volume at stable conditions of temperature. The combination of Henry's and gas pressure laws leads to the conclusion that in stable conditions whenever microbubble gets smaller gas pressure into it elevates and gas diffuses outside, and when microbubble magnitudes gas pressure into it gets lower and gas diffuses into it.

It has previously been demonstrated that some chemical reactions which occur in liquid can be accelerated by ultrasound^{52,53} considerably. The influence of high intensity ultrasounds in liquids causes in general non-linear propagation and effects like: acoustic streaming, sound-sound interaction, and acoustic heating.⁵³ Performance of ultrasound waves above 20 kHz to liquid induce air microbubble to oscillate around its equilibrium axon by the greater intention of oscillation.⁵⁴ During oscillation, bubble expands and the amount of gas that enters into it is more than the one that will escape during construction because diffusion is proportional to the surface of microbubble.^{54,55} The difference in the amount of gas getting in during the expansion compared to the amount getting out during the construction of the microbubble is small in

each oscillation cycle but after several cycles it becomes greater and this is defined as rectified diffusion. The microbubble grows because of rectified diffusion from equilibrium size to resonance one and finally breaks emitting high temperature, free radicals and microjets.^{53,45} The bubble growth is inhibited by the inertia and the viscosity of the surrounding medium. A time constant can be estimated for both of them predicting the time that growth process will start. If the sum of the inertial start-up time, and the viscous start-up time is equal or larger than a specific fraction of an acoustic period, the bubble growth won't start before the acoustic phase cycle becomes positive and the bubble begins to decelerate before it collapses.⁵⁶ The number of microbubbles is proportional to the ultrasound energy, and cavitation has self-inhibitory effects because of increase of the temperature and sound scattering in ultrasound liquid.⁵⁰

A relative physical theory about this phenomenon was initially developed by Minnaert at 1933. According to this theory gas bubbles in water will oscillate influenced by a pressure field. The mathematical analysis used was similar to the one used by physicists to solve problems dealing with vibrating masses and springs and he observed linear conditions concerning volume changes in the bubble.^{53,57} Resonance frequency is a property of the microbubble that is related to the identity of gas and liquid and to the radius of the microbubble. It is calculated by Minnaert's equation. It is proportional to the ratio of the specific heats for the gas and the prevailing hydrostatic pressure and inversely proportional to the liquid density, and to the equilibrium radius of the bubble. The last expression is more valid for air and water. Resonance frequency can be decreased by several factors like viscosity, temperature and acoustic radiation.⁵⁷ Several observations of the bubble dynamic have been understood by the help of Minnaert's theory. Thus, the acceptance that the momentary force of a bubble in a sound field is proportional both to its volume and to the gradient of pressure into the surrounding liquid, has guided to interesting results about time related forces and motions. The conclusions that were confirmed experimentally are the following: bubbles smaller than resonance size coalesces in water, form large bubbles and in standing-wave fields move to the pressure maxima.⁵³ The first phenomenon partly explains the degassing process, and the expulsion of gases.^{57,58} In solutions where the bubbles are covered with organic material the formation of large bubbles may be avoided but foam will form. The second phenomenon guides to coalescence of bubbles and formation of larger ones until bubble diameter reaches the resonance value. As this happens the bubbles oscillate

with increasing amplitude. Bubbles, greater than resonance size, move to pressure minima where they're inactive. Acceleration of chemical reactions which is associated with cavitation cannot be predicted by linear theory but the development of non-linear equations has given satisfactory explanations.⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ At a basic level, these single bubble theories describe the reaction of the bubble at the local sound field and that the pressure field will be modified by the way sound is scattered by neighboring bubbles. The created non-uniform sound field will cause a consequent inhomogeneous bubble distribution. Such a distribution can direct and amplify ultrasonic waves, can acoustically isolate regions of the sample, and elsewhere localize the cavitation activity to discrete "hot spots". As a result, portions of the sample may undergo intense sonochemical activity, degassing, erosion, etc., whilst other areas remain relatively unaffected. Techniques exist to control such situations where they are desirable, where a more uniform handling of the sample is desired.^{44,62} Moreover, theories for losses of acoustic energy connected to the oscillating bubbles were developed.⁵³

A bubble in a sound field is not influenced exclusively by the sound pressure force of the sound field but by other forces too. Pressure gradients will give a bubble translational motion and cause it to lose its stability in a standing sound field.^{63,64} The spherical stability of the bubble is limited if it oscillates too hard.^{65,66} The transitory phenomenon of the formation and movement of bubbles or cavities in liquids during the low pressure portion of a pressure wave cycle induced by ultrasound is termed ultrasound cavitation.⁵¹ It depends on dumping, liquid mass and stiffness of gas, and a high cavitation target is achieved by low frequency ultrasound since increased ultrasound frequency decreases available time for cavitation.⁵⁰ The cavitation threshold for pure liquids is accounted for by the strength of the bonds between its molecules. This threshold must be overcome by a correspondingly strong tension. For a pure or a homogenous liquid subjected to static tension is defined as homogenous nucleation threshold.^{53,67} The rupture of real liquids does not demand high negative pressures and the cavitation threshold is called "the heterogeneous nucleation threshold" attributed to the heterogeneities present in liquids.^{53,68,69} Heterogeneities may be solid particles, tiny bubbles, ionizing particles or the walls of the container and they are called cavitation nuclei.⁷⁰ The most possible nuclei for cavitation are gassed trapped in conical cracks on a hydrophobic surface and microbubbles protected from dissolution by substances of their surface that prevent the transport of gas from the bubble to the liquid.^{71,72}

Besides static tension, liquids are ruptured by acoustic waves or by converting pressure waves to tension waves after reflection on a free surface.^{73,74} In acoustic cavitation the pressure of the sound wave must be as high as the cavitation threshold, although the negative pressure causes the rupture of the liquid. A lot of bubbles of different sizes oscillate and interact in complex ways to form clusters, filaments and clouds.^{75,76} There are two main types of acoustic cavitation: symmetric and asymmetric. Symmetric is divided to stable and inertial one and the term symmetric means that the microbubbles are free-floating, spherically symmetric, and that all points of their surface act on the same way. At stable cavitation there is a small expansion of the bubble's beam, smaller than ten percent of equilibrium radius during oscillation, and stiffness of gas dominate these dynamics.³⁷ The bubble oscillates during many cycles before collapse.⁵¹ This kind of cavitation results in the emission of subharmonics of the half frequency of sonication and submultiples. At inertial or transient cavitation excursions are more than twice the equilibrium radius and the bubble which gets bigger collapses suddenly in one pressure wave cycle.^{51,53} Temperature and pressure inside the bubble can be very high in this case, and the collapse of the microbubble is accompanied by light emission and hydroxyl free radicals' production.⁵³ In the border of the two types of cavitation a bubble may be driven and remain oscillating and stable in diameter and emitting light for many minutes.⁵¹ Asymmetric kind of cavitation is more possible in a distance smaller than ten microbubble-diameters away from a solid surface and is the main way that ultrasound exerts its action.⁵⁰

The collapse of the microbubble is characterized by increased pressure on its side away from solid surface, and extraction of a high velocity liquid jet towards the surface. The liquid jet is formed by the disturbance of the spherical symmetry of the surroundings of the bubble by a solid wall, a free surface, another bubble, gravity, bubble translation, or a shock wave. The main result of cavitation caused by the sonication method to biofilm is its destruction and the detachment of alive bacteria as they both seem to be more sensitive to mechanical pressure than to chemical pressure.⁵⁰ The high temperature that is produced is supposed to be the main cause for these actions.⁴⁹

2.3 Technical principles

Sonication can be used for specific kinds of implants like orthopedic, breast, neurosurgical, cardiological electrophysiology apparatus and generally for any kind of implant that can be taken by the body in an aseptic way, but it cannot be used for bone species

and tissues, since implants from non-aseptic areas of the body can be used under restrictions.^{77,78} There are slightly different protocols for the method which agree in general that implants have to be received and examined by the laboratory within four to six hours after their subtraction. Otherwise implant have to be covered by Ringer Solution or 0,9% NaCl and to be retained at room temperature until the onset of the procedure.⁷⁹ The implant is carried into special propylene, air-tight, autoclavable containers of different volumes and shapes depending on the volume, the type and the length of the explanted implant, from the operating room to the laboratory² (fig.1). The implant is then covered by Ringer solution or by NaCl 0,9% and is moved strongly by hand or vortex for 30 sec in order a partial degassing of the implant covering fluid to be succeeded in. The container is placed in an ultrasound water bath and is exposed to the ultrasound waves of 100% intention, around 40 kHz frequency, and 0,22+/- 0,04 Watt/cm² for 1 to 5 minutes^{17,89} (fig 2).

The container is moved strongly again by hand or vortex for 30 sec. After the ultrasound performance 0,1 ml of the fluid is inoculated onto blood, chocolate and Brucella agar (100 µL each one), 3-4 ml are inoculated in thioglycolate broth. Furthermore, approximately 10 ml of sonication fluid are placed to sterilized tubes and remain on -80° C for at least one month, in case more tests have been requested.^{1,79} Specimens are handled aseptically in a laminar flow-safety cabinet.² Culture plates are properly incubated up to 14 days in order all of the causative agents compromising the anaerobes to be detected and their susceptibility testing to be performed.^{22,24}

Positivity cut-off is 5 CFU per plate, especially for the prostheses.^{17,22} Gram staining of the sediment by centrifuging 200 ml of sonication fluid at 2600 rpm for 15 minutes possesses low sensitivity for revealing the responsible bacteria causing Prosthetic Joint Infections.¹⁷ Alternatively to the conventional culture-based methods, molecular techniques can be combined to the sonication method but their value and usefulness is still under estimation.^{12,80,88,89}

2.4 Clinical and technical research aspects of sonication

The sonication method seems to be very effective in the diagnosis of implant associated infections because of its ability in detaching biofilm and this is supported by several clinical and laboratory studies that have investigated the method and its results and given interesting data.⁸¹⁻⁸³ The studies on sonication as a diagnostic method of implant related infections move on two main axons. The one is its effectiveness comparatively to other methods of diagnosis of implant infections as well as its combination to them, and the other is its technical improvement in order to have better outcomes. Thus, some of the studies of this kind show that the sonication method is more sensitive and of almost equal specificity compared to periprosthetic tissue cultures for the diagnosis of prosthetic infections.^{17,22} Better results have also been achieved by the sonication method experiments when comparing sonication and scraping practices for detaching bacteria from discs.⁸¹ Molecular methods and direct immunofluorescence were found less sensitive in some studies or not superior comparati-

Figure 1 Container with an orthopaedic implant partially covered by sonication fluid.

Figure 2 Ultrasound bath.

vely to conventional cultures.^{12,80} However, investigation in this area continues giving interesting results, since molecular methods perform increased sensitivity compared to conventional ones in patients who previously received antibiotics.^{22,23,84} Moreover, microbial cultures seem to perform decreased sensitivity for several reasons like short incubation time, antibiotic treatment, and loss of alive bacteria during transport.²⁴ Concerning the modification of technical characteristics of the method, there is data supporting that relative short times of ultrasonication have better results than longer ones on detecting biofilm-formatting bacteria either by typical cultures or by polymerase chain reaction. A remarkable protocol for the method which was performed on an experiment dealing with the temperature of the sonication buffer and the time of sonication has shown optimum results at 22°C for 7 min. This protocol helps the survival of gram-negative bacteria, since gram positive bacteria seem to be more resistant.²¹

A similar study has shown that short times of sonication up to one-minute help releasing and keeping *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria alive and detectable either by cultures or molecular techniques, and longer times of sonication especially more than five minutes destroy bacteria and inhibit their detection by cultures, but not by molecular methods.⁸⁵ Culture of the so-

nication fluid into blood culture bottles was seen to improve the diagnosis of implant associated infections.^{86,88,89} Other recent studies show better results by centrifugation of the sonication fluid rather than by its filtration through special membranes, in the diagnosis of bacteria responsible for infection of arthroplasty implants, and improvement of specificity and sensitivity when using 400-500 ml of Ringer's solution in containers.^{22,87}

3. Conclusions

Sonication assay using low frequency ultrasound waves seems to have great advantages comparatively to other conventional and newer methods on solving diagnostic problems of implant associated infections. Its ability to destroy biofilm causing asymmetric cavitation of air bubbles in an aquatic mean makes it very effective, sensitive and specific, and additionally very simple and of low cost-effectiveness quotient. It's a sophisticated method, based on classical principles of physics about the pressure of gases in a liquid and cavitation and it has many implementations on diagnostic, research and experimental field of implant associated infections. Biofilm, the source of implant related infections and the main target of the sonication method, is a very complicated structure of interesting properties concerning the protection of microorganisms that constitute it, and a serious cause of problems in the diagnosis and therapy of implant associated infections. It would be of great importance for further research to be carried out about the advantages of the sonication method in comparison to other conventional and newer methods, the importance and usefulness of its possible combination with them with priority to molecular methods and for technical modification of sonication that could give better diagnostic results to proceed. Further studies on the biofilm's nature and properties and on the performance of ultrasound waves in the fields of diagnosis and basic research of implant associated infections may have a lot to offer to this crucial field of Clinical Microbiology.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Περίληψη

Βασικές αρχές της μεθόδου υπερήχησης για την απόσπαση ζώντων μικροοργανισμών εμπεδωμένων εντός βιομεμβράνης στην επιφάνεια εμφυτεύματος

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Η μέθοδος της υπερήχησης έχει χρησιμοποιηθεί την τελευταία δεκαετία για τη διάγνωση λοιμώξεων που σχετίζονται με εμφυτεύματα, οι οποίες αποτελούν μια σοβαρότατη επιπλοκή των χειρουργικών τεχνικών που χρησιμοποιούν –“εμφυτεύουν” ξένα σώματα. Είναι μια σχετικά νέα μέθοδος που αναπτύσσεται ταχέως και η οποία υπόσχεται πολλά για την επίλυση διαγνωστικών και θεραπευτικών προβλημάτων της Κλινικής Μικροβιολογίας. Η βασική ιδέα αυτής της μεθόδου είναι η αποκόλληση ζώντων βακτηρίων που είναι εμπεδωμένα και σχηματίζουν τη βιομεμβράνη, η οποία καλύπτει το εμφύτευμα. Ο σχηματισμός της βιομεμβράνης δημιουργεί σοβαρές δυσκολίες στην ανίχνευση των παθογόνων που προκαλούν λοιμώξεις από εμφύτευμα με τη χρήση των συμβατικών μεθόδων μικροβιολογίας, καθώς και στην επακόλουθη αντιμικροβιακή χημειοθεραπεία. Η απόσπαση από τη βιομεμβράνη ζώντων μικροβίων επιτυγχάνεται με τη χρήση υπερηχητικών κυμάτων χαμηλής συχνότητας που προκαλούν ασύμμετρη σπηλαίωση σε μικροφουσαλίδες του υγρού υπερήχησης πάνω στην επιφάνεια του εξεταζόμενου εμφυτεύματος. Στη συνέχεια το εμπλουτισμένο με τα μικρόβια της βιομεμβράνης υγρό της υπερήχησης καλλιεργείται ποσοτικά ή/και εξετάζεται με μοριακές τεχνικές. Η λεπτομερής περιγραφή και ανάλυση των βασικών αρχών της μεθόδου υπερήχησης θα αυξήσει τις γνώσεις μας και θα βοηθήσει πολύ στη βελτίωση και την εξέλιξή της. Σε αυτή τη μελέτη αναφέρονται λεπτομερώς οι βασικές αρχές της Φυσικής, αρχές της Βιολογίας καθώς και τεχνικές αρχές που άπτονται της μεθόδου της υπερήχησης καθώς και τις ερευνητικές της πτυχές και εξάγονται συμπεράσματα σχετικά με την αξία και τις προοπτικές της, εστιάζοντας στη διάγνωση των λοιμώξεων που σχετίζονται με εμφυτεύματα.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

λοιμώξεις σχετιζόμενες με εμφυτεύματα, βιομεμβράνη, μέθοδος υπερήχησης, μικροφουσαλίδες, ασύμμετρική σπηλαίωση

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